

26 defects is increased by 8.89% and 2.04%, respectively, demonstrating the validity and
27 authenticity of the generated data. This method provides reliable technical support for
28 solving the small sample problem in concrete defect detection.

29 **Keywords:** Fair-faced concrete; Generative adversarial network; Image augmentation;
30 Self-attention mechanism; Gradient penalty

31 **Abbreviations:** Wasserstein generative adversarial network, SAWGAN-GP; Fréchet
32 inception distance, FID; Wasserstein generative adversarial network, WGAN;
33 Generative adversarial networks, GANs; Conditional variational autoencoder,
34 DCCVAE; Dual discriminator Wasserstein generative adversarial network, D2WGAN;
35 Surface defect generative adversarial network, SDGAN; Variational autoencoding,
36 VAE; Electrocardiogram, ECG; One-dimensional convolutional neural network,
37 1DCNN; Self-attention deep convolutional generative adversarial network, SAGAN;
38 Earth mover distance, EMD; Generated distribution, P_g ; Real distribution, P_r ; Self-
39 attention mechanism, SA; Gradient penalty, GP

40 **1. Introduction**

41 With the rapid development of the construction industry, fair-faced concrete, as an
42 important building material, is widely used due to its natural and simple appearance, as
43 well as high structural strength. However, surface defects of plain concrete (such as
44 cracks, holes, peeling, etc.) often affect the aesthetics and durability of buildings.
45 Therefore, timely and accurate detection and repair of these defects have become an
46 important task of building quality control. Traditional defect detection methods mostly
47 rely on manual inspection, which is inefficient and can be easily interfered with by
48 human factors, and thus cannot meet the large-scale and efficient detection needs of
49 modern buildings.

50 In recent years, as artificial intelligence technologies rapidly develop, automated

51 defect detection methods based on deep learning have been emerging. Deep learning
52 has demonstrated powerful capabilities in image recognition and classification tasks,
53 and can learn useful features from large amounts of data, thereby improving the
54 accuracy of defect detection. Nevertheless, the accuracy of deep learning models
55 heavily depends on a large number of high-quality annotated datasets. In practical
56 applications, the collection of defect images is usually constrained by time, costs, and
57 site conditions, usually resulting in insufficient scale and a single type of training
58 datasets. This issue seriously affects the generalization ability and recognition accuracy
59 of the model, as deep learning methods cannot fully learn the diversity of defect images
60 in the case of insufficient datasets, which leads to unstable performance of the model.
61 Especially, in the detection task of fair-faced concrete defects, owing to the scarcity of
62 image samples of certain defect types, deep learning models are prone to overfitting or
63 poor generalization problems, and cannot effectively identify various defects.

64 To alleviate the problem of data scarcity, data augmentation technologies have
65 been developed. Traditional data augmentation approaches mainly include single-
66 sample augmentation and multi-sample augmentation. Single-sample data
67 augmentation changes the appearance, angle, size or perspective of a single image
68 through operations (such as rotation, flipping, scaling, translation, cropping, and
69 deformation), and adding noise to increase the diversity of data. Multi-sample data
70 augmentation, such as Mixup [1] and Mosaic [2], mixes the features of multiple samples
71 to generate new synthetic samples. However, these traditional methods are essentially
72 transformations or combinations of existing data. It is difficult to fundamentally solve

73 the problems of small samples and sample imbalance using these techniques, as the
74 diversity and authenticity of the generated samples are still limited.

75 In contrast, generative adversarial networks (GANs) [3] perform as a powerful
76 unsupervised generative model that can learn the underlying distribution of data, and
77 generate highly realistic new samples through adversarial training of generators and
78 discriminators. Compared with traditional enhancement methods, GANs can generate
79 more diverse and realistic images, effectively expand the dataset, and thus, significantly
80 improve the generalization ability of the model, particularly when samples are scarce
81 or the categories are unbalanced. This advantage has been verified in several areas. In
82 the agricultural field, GANs have been widely used in crop disease detection. Li et al.
83 [4] successfully used GANs for data enhancement of corn disease images with a small
84 sample size through an improved DCGAN model, which significantly improved the
85 accuracy of disease detection. In addition, Xu et al. [5] combined GANs technology
86 with deep convolutional neural networks to generate a large number of synthetic leaf
87 images for leaf recognition tasks, further expanding the dataset and enhancing the
88 recognition performance of the model in different seasons and environments. Han et al.
89 [6] proposed a data enhancement method for sweet cherries with improved DCGAN.
90 By introducing multi-scale residual blocks and CBAM attention mechanism, high-
91 quality defective images of sweet cherries were generated, which effectively tackled
92 the data imbalance problem, and improved the accuracy of the sweet cherry
93 classification model. Also, Jordan et al. [7] pruned the CGAN model for image
94 generation of fruits.

95 In the field of industrial defect detection, Zhao et al. [8] proposed a GANs-based
96 method for the enhancement of workpiece image data. Through the self-attention
97 mechanism and the improved residual network, high-quality workpiece defect images
98 were generated, which addressed the common blur and unreality problems of traditional
99 image generation with GANs. Wang et al. [9] raised a GANs method, named auxiliary
100 classifier spectral normalization, to enhance the feature database of surface damage
101 samples of conveyor belt. In order to avoid the possible collapse of DCGAN, Liu et al.
102 [10] introduced the focal loss confidence function to participate in the training process,
103 which significantly addressed the imbalance between the precision and recall rate of
104 the detection model. Bu et al. [11] integrated the conditional variational autoencoder
105 (DCCVAE), the auxiliary conditional Wasserstein GANs, and gradient penalty based
106 on DCNN, to gradually expand and generate various defect images of ship coating,
107 which addressed the overfitting problem attributed to data imbalance.

108 In recent years, GANs have gradually emerged in the research area of building
109 structure, which show great potential. Deng et al. [12] added a new DG2 adversarial
110 loss to GANs to improve the quality of concrete crack image generation. Li and Zhao
111 [13] proposed a synthesis method for high-resolution concrete damage image using a
112 conditional GANs, whose synthesized images presented excellent authenticity. Notably,
113 GANs is still under-investigated in the generation of concrete defect images. Qin et al.
114 [14] used DCGAN to generate similar GPR (ground penetrating radar) images for
115 tunnel lining, which were added to the training set. the approach improved the
116 recognition accuracy of rigid ribs, empty linings and initial lining thickness by 2%-4%,

117 revealing the feasibility of DCGAN to generate GPR images. Que et al. [15] used
118 improved DCGAN to expand various obvious disease images of pavements, which
119 effectively enhanced the accuracy of the classification network.

120 In addition, regarding specific structure, Nguyen et al. [16] established D2GAN to
121 solve the diversity problem in the generation of defect images. A diverse reward
122 mechanism was integrated into the discriminator, encouraging the generation of
123 different images through distinguishing generated features from real features. Liu et al.
124 [17] proposed a dual discriminator Wasserstein generative adversarial network
125 (D2WGAN), which uses KL divergence and reverse KL divergence to optimize the
126 generative model to generate rich and diverse samples. Zhang et al. [18] developed
127 DefectGAN, which can generate a variety of defect images by introducing noise during
128 encoding and decoding. However, the generated defect images may include samples
129 completely imperceptible or unnecessary. Moreover, Niu et al. [19] proposed a surface
130 defect generative adversarial network (SDGAN), which adds a discriminator to the
131 network architecture to facilitate the generation of different features. Hao et al. [20]
132 established an improved DCGAN model, which introduces an update rule with dual
133 time scale, cancels the normalization operation of the generator, and uses a
134 discriminator for the detection of conveyor belt surface defects. Guo et al. [21]
135 developed an MCC-CycleGAN model to enhance the dataset using a public steel
136 dataset and a limited-size conveyor dataset to achieve unpaired image-to-image
137 conversion to improve the accuracy of defect detection. Du et al. [22] proposed a data
138 augmentation algorithm that combines variational autoencoding (VAE) and ACGAN to

139 enlarge the size of a two-dimensional electrocardiogram (ECG) image dataset, thus
140 improving the sensitivity of minority groups. Shao et al. [23] used a one-dimensional
141 convolutional neural network (1DCNN) as the building block of the generator and the
142 discriminator under the ACGAN framework. Additionally, Zhang et al. [24] integrated
143 the self-attention mechanism with DCGAN and employed a spectral normalization
144 method in the generator, to form a self-attention deep convolutional generative
145 adversarial network (SAGAN), which can significantly enhance detailed features of
146 generated images and benefit model convergence.

147 In order to tackle the insufficient generalization ability of deep learning models
148 attributed to the scarcity of training data for the surface defect detection of fair-faced
149 concrete, this study proposed a method to expand the surface defect image samples of
150 fair-faced concrete based on SAWGAN-GP (Self-Attention Wasserstein GANs with
151 Gradient Penalty). As a powerful data augmentation technology, GANs can generate
152 images similar to real samples through game training of generators and discriminators,
153 therefore expanding the dataset and overcoming the problems of data imbalance and
154 sample insufficiency. Specifically, SAWGAN-GP combines the self-attention
155 mechanism, Wasserstein GANs, and gradient penalty technology to generate high-
156 quality defect images, enhance the diversity and representativeness of the training
157 dataset, and thus improve the training effect and increase the detection accuracy of the
158 deep learning model.

159 **2. SAWGAN-GP network for apparent image augmentation**

160 *2.1. Theoretical basis*

161 WGAN (Wasserstein generative adversarial network) is developed [25] to solve
162 the problems of instability and mode collapse encountered by traditional GANs during
163 training. In traditional GANs, the loss function relies on conventional divergence
164 techniques, such as JS(Jensen-Shannon Divergence), to measure the difference between
165 the generated data distribution and the real data distribution. Nevertheless, this design
166 often leads to the gradient vanishing phenomenon when the generated distribution and
167 the real distribution do not overlap significantly [26]. As a result, the generator cannot
168 get effective feedback, which impedes the training from continuing, and mode collapse
169 is prone to occur. To solve this problem, WGAN introduces Wasserstein distance (also
170 known as Earth Mover Distance (EMD)) to replace JS divergence, which is illustrated
171 in Figure 1. It characterizes the difference between the generated distribution (P_g) and
172 the real distribution (P_r) through measuring the minimum transportation cost between
173 the distributions [27], i.e., the amount of work required to move P_g to P_r .

174

175

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of Wasserstein distance

176

The Wasserstein distance is defined as follows:

177

$$W(P_r, P_g) = \inf_{\Pi(P_r, P_g)} E_{(x, y) \sim \gamma} [\|x - y\|]$$

178 where γ is the joint distribution; $\Pi(P_r, P_g)$ is the set of possible joint distributions
179 between P_r and P_g ; for γ , $E_{(x,y)\sim\gamma}[\|x-y\|]$ calculates the expected value of the moving
180 distance $\|x-y\|$ from point x in distribution P_g to point y in distribution P_r . This moving
181 distance is usually the Euclidean distance, but can also be other metrics. Directly
182 measuring the distance between two distributions, the Wasserstein distance avoids the
183 gradient vanishing problem usually associated with the JS divergence when the
184 distributions do not overlap. This feature ensures that the generator can gradually
185 optimize the generated samples through a stable gradient signal, even if the initial
186 generation quality is poor [28]. Therefore, the loss function of
187 WGAN($\min_G \max_D V(D, G) = E_{x \sim p_{data(x)}} [\log D(x)] + E_{z \sim p_z} [\log(1 - D(G(z)))]$) is designed as:

$$188 \quad L_{WGAN} = E_{x \sim p_r} [D(x)] - E_{z \sim p_z} [D(G(z))]$$

189 It can be seen that the discriminator in WGAN no longer outputs a probability
190 ranging from 0 to 1, but gives a real number score for the authenticity of the sample.
191 The goal of the generator is to minimize the score $D(G(z))$ of the generated sample $G(z)$,
192 as it hopes the score difference between the generated sample and the real sample will
193 gradually decrease. Compared with the " $\log(1 - D(G(z)))$ " term in traditional GANs, the
194 scoring mechanism of WGAN can provide a smoother optimization path when the
195 sample distribution difference is large, thereby avoiding the mode collapse problem.

196 2.2. Improvement of network structure

197 2.2.1. Self-attention mechanism

198 The attention mechanism is initially proposed in the area of natural language
199 processing [29]. Its core idea is to enable the model to dynamically focus on important
200 information in the input through calculating the correlation between different parts of
201 the input. Unlike traditional convolution operations, the attention mechanism can
202 adaptively assign different weights to features at different positions according to task

203 requirements, thus capturing more critical contextual information. This mechanism is
 204 originally applied to process sequence data (e.g., text). With the development of
 205 research, the mechanism has shown strong application potential in image processing
 206 tasks [30].

207 The self-attention mechanism (SA) is a special form of the attention mechanism
 208 for describing long-distance dependencies by calculating the similarity between
 209 features in the same input [31]. In image generation tasks, SA enables the generator and
 210 discriminator to "see" the entire image globally, instead of being limited to the receptive
 211 field of the local convolution kernel, therefore, it can better capture the associations
 212 between distant pixels in the image. This is crucial for image generation with rich
 213 details and global consistency. The specific calculation process of the self-attention
 214 mechanism can be described by the following formula:

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = \text{soft max}(QK^T / \sqrt{d_k})V$$

215 where, Q – query, K – key, and V – value, are matrices obtained by linearly transforming
 216 input features; d_k is the dimension of the key.

218 By calculating the similarity between the query and the key, the model can weigh
 219 the features in the value matrix to obtain an enhanced feature representation. Through
 220 this mechanism, the self-attention mechanism can describe the dependencies between
 221 distant pixels in the image, whose operation flow is illustrated in Figure 2.

222

223 Figure 2. Schematic of the self-attention mechanism structure

224 2.2.2. Residual block

225 The residual block is used to solve the problems of common gradient vanishing
226 and gradient exploding in deep neural networks [32]. In deep neural networks, as the
227 number of network layers increases, model training tends to become increasingly
228 difficult. The performance of the model may not necessarily improve with the depth of
229 the network, and may even degenerate. The utilization of the residual block effectively
230 alleviates this challenge and significantly improves the training effect of deep neural
231 networks. The key point lies in the introduction of the skip connection, which allows
232 each layer of the network to learn the transformation of input features, while also
233 directly passing input information to subsequent layers. This characteristic allows the
234 network to only learn the residual between input and output in each layer, rather than
235 directly fitting complex input-output mappings, as shown in the formula:

236
$$y = F(x, \{W_i\}) + X$$

237 where y is the output feature; x is the input feature; W_i is the network weight; $F(x, \{W_i\})$
238 denotes the convolution operation and nonlinear transformation of the input feature;
239 $F(x, \{W_i\})$ and X are added through jump connections to generate the final output.
240 Through this design, the residual block allows the network to learn more complex
241 features without losing the original basic information. Figure 3 shows the residual
242 module.

243

Figure 3. Residual module [32] (ReLU: Rectified Linear Unit)

2.2.3. Loss function

During the training process of GANs, the choice of loss function has a significant impact on the training effect of the model. Traditional loss functions can work effectively in certain cases, but they often face challenges in practical applications, such as training instability, mode collapse and gradient disappearance. To solve these issues, the gradient penalty (GP) [28] is adopted as an effective optimization method, especially in the framework of WGAN.

The main purpose of GP is to ensure that the discriminator satisfies the Lipschitz continuity condition [33] to avoid extreme gradient values during training. By introducing the GP term, the model can effectively balance the training process between the generator and the discriminator, which ensures a smooth transition between the generated and real samples. Its loss function can be expressed as:

$$L_{GP} = \lambda \cdot E_{\hat{x} \sim p_{\hat{x}}} [(\|\nabla_{\hat{x}} D(\hat{x})\|_2 - 1)^2]$$

where \hat{x} is the sample obtained by interpolation between the real sample and the generated sample; $D(\hat{x})$ is the score of the discriminator on the sample; λ is the hyperparameter of the penalty strength. By limiting the gradient of the interpolated sample, the model can effectively prevent instability during the training process, therefore improving the quality of the generated images.

3. Data collection and configuration

3.1. Experimental data set and configuration

The data sets required for the experiment are collected by drones. The collection locations involve two public buildings that have been put into use, and three power plants under construction. The public buildings are the Kunpeng Pavilion and the

268 Academician Center Landscape Corridor in Ningbo City, and the power plants are the
269 China Resources Power Wenzhou Power Plant in Wenzhou City, the Taizhou No. 2
270 Power Plant in Taizhou City, and the Zhejiang Energy Power Plant in Ningbo City.
271 Figure 4 shows these collection locations.

(a) Kunpeng Pavilion

(b) Academician Center Landscape Corridor

(c) China Resources Power Wenzhou Power

(d) Tai-2 Power Plant

Plant

272 Figure 4. Image acquisition locations

273 Kunpeng Pavilion is a landmark building with large-span, multi-curved and
 274 specially-shaped fair-faced concrete. Its surface area of fair-faced concrete exceeds
 275 8,000 square meters. The building widely uses complex structural forms, such as curved
 276 walls, specially-shaped columns and cantilevered curved panels. The Academician
 277 Center is a building with a long and narrow linear structure, which combines modern
 278 architectural style with complicated functional requirements. The three power plants
 279 are typical industrial buildings using a large number of fair-faced concrete structures,
 280 mainly including chimneys, cooling towers, firewalls and frame beams. Under a
 281 complex environment for a long time, these fair-faced concrete surfaces are prone to
 282 defects, such as cracks and peeling, that affect the durability and safety of the structures.

283 The surface types of fair-faced concrete are divided into 2 major categories and 8
 284 minor categories, and the resolution of each image is 256×256 pixels. The data details
 285 are shown in Table 1, and the difference between the surface images of different fair-
 286 faced concrete is shown in Figure 4.

287 Table 1. List of image datasets for fair-faced concrete surface

Surface	Appearance type	Number of images
Defective surface	Efflorescence	867
	Cracks	1,281
	Holes	710
	Rust	882
	Peeling	564
Normal surface	Bolt holes	857

Horizontal seams

860

Vertical seams

855

288

(a) Efflorescence

(b) Cracks

(c) Holes

(d) Peeling

(e) Rust

(f) Horizontal seams

(g) Vertical seams

(h) Bolt toles

289

Figure 4. Surface image of fair-faced concrete

290

In order to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed generation model for

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fair-faced concrete surface images, this study designs a series of experiments to

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evaluate the performance of different model architectures regarding the quality of

293 generated images and training stability. The experimental environment involved in this
 294 section is summarised in Table 2.

295 Table 2. Experimental environment information

Type	Environment components	Environment configuration
Hardware	CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-12400F
	GPU	NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4060
	RAM	16.0 GB
Software	Operating system	Windows 11
	CUDA	11.8
	Programming language	Python 3.9
	Deep learning framework	PyTorch2.0.0

296 **4. Experimental results**

297 *4.1. Comparison of loss values*

298 *4.1.1. Basic models*

299 Three basic models were selected for comparison: WGAN, DCGAN, and ACGAN.
 300 From the data in Figure 5 (a) and Table 3, the generator loss of WGAN showed a slow
 301 upward trend during the training process, which was relatively stable at the beginning.
 302 The loss was 163.645 at 1,000 iterations. Later, it reached 223.137 at 3,000 iterations,
 303 and slightly increased to 235.924 at 5,000 iterations. The phenomenon indicates that
 304 the generator gradually approached the target distribution, and the training process was
 305 stable without significant fluctuations. In contrast, the generator loss of DCGAN
 306 fluctuated significantly – the loss was as small as 22.411 at the initial 1,000 iterations,
 307 but as the training progressed, it jumped to 193.929 at 3,000 iterations and further rose
 308 to 521.551 at 5,000 iterations. The considerable fluctuations in the loss value prevented

309 the generator from continuously capturing the details of the target distribution, thus
 310 affecting the generation effect. The loss of ACGAN was relatively stable at the
 311 beginning, which was 19.774 at 1,000 iterations. However, as the training progressed,
 312 it rapidly increased to 165.234 at 3,000 iterations and 399.998 at 5,000 iterations,
 313 indicating instability issues in the training and the continuous learning effect could not
 314 be maintained. For the discriminator loss, as illustrated in Figure 5 (b), the loss of
 315 WGAN gradually decreased and stabilized, showing that the interaction between the
 316 discriminator and the generator was relatively balanced and the training process was
 317 stable. The losses of DCGAN and ACGAN fluctuated severely. Although the loss of
 318 DCGAN was low at the beginning of training, it then rose sharply, with a large
 319 fluctuation range from a minimum of 1,096.52 to a maximum of 1,858.223, presenting
 320 significant instability during the training process. The loss of ACGAN also showed a
 321 similar fluctuation trend.

Figure 5. Loss curves

Table 3. Comparison of loss values at different iterations

Iteration	1,000	3,000	5,000
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Model			
WGAN	163.645	223.137	235.924
DCGAN	22.411	193.929	521.551
ACGAN	19.774	165.234	399.998

322 4.1.2. Improved WGAN model

323 The generator loss curve (Figure 6) and the data (Table 4) showed that the
324 performance of SAWGAN, WGAN-GP, and SAWGAN-GP was significantly different
325 from that of WGAN. SAWGAN reduced fluctuations by introducing a self-attention
326 mechanism, with a maximum loss of 188.57. After 2,500 iterations, the loss gradually
327 stabilized, with a fluctuation range of 18.78. Compared with WGAN, the loss
328 fluctuation of SAWGAN was significantly reduced, showing better stability and
329 optimization effect. WGAN-GP further improved the stability of the generator through
330 the gradient penalty mechanism. Its maximum loss value was 165.92, the minimum was
331 148.63, and the fluctuation range was 17.28. In comparison with SAWGAN and
332 WGAN, WGAN-GP presents smaller fluctuations in loss control, whose loss value
333 remained at a low level, demonstrating the advantages of the gradient penalty
334 mechanism in limiting loss fluctuations and improving training stability. SAWGAN-
335 GP, which combined the self-attention mechanism and the gradient penalty mechanism,
336 showed the best stability after 2,500 iterations. With the maximum loss of 70.87 and
337 the minimum loss of 54.81, its fluctuation range was 16.06, which was much lower than
338 other models. Through the integration of the two mechanisms, the method effectively
339 reduced the fluctuation of the loss, and showed higher efficiency and better training
340 stability.

Figure 6. Generator loss curves

Table 4. Maximum/minimum generation loss values of different models

Model	Maximum loss	Minimum loss (after 2,500 iterations)	Fluctuation range
WGAN	239.86	213.35	26.51
SAWGAN	188.57	169.79	18.78
WGAN-GP	165.92	148.63	17.28
SAWGAN-GP	70.87	54.81	16.06

With respect to discriminator loss, WGAN-GP and SAWGAN were also significantly better than WGAN. For WGAN-GP, the maximum loss was 22.14, the minimum loss was 0.05, and the fluctuation range was 22.09. While SAWGAN, the corresponding values were 69.75, 0.01, and 69.74, respectively. Both of them showed small loss fluctuations during training. On the other hand, WGAN had a maximum loss of 500.10 and a minimum loss of 1.23, resulting in a fluctuation range of up to 498.87. The large loss fluctuation indicated its poor optimization performance. The local magnification in Figure 7 further highlighted that the losses of SAWGAN and WGAN-GP tended to stabilize in the later stages of training, where their fluctuation ranges were significantly reduced. The maximum loss of SAWGAN-GP was only 3.38, while the

354 minimum loss reached 0.00, resulting in a small fluctuation range of 3.38, showing its
 355 extremely high stability.

356

357

Figure 7. Discriminator loss curves

358

Table 5. Maximum/minimum discriminant loss values of different models

Model	Maximum loss	Minimum loss (after 2, 500 iterations)	Fluctuation range
WGAN	183.75	1.23	182.52
SAWGAN	22.78	0.01	22.77
WGAN-GP	10.27	0.05	10.23
SAWGAN-GP	1.45	0.00	1.45

359

4.1.3. Hyperparameter adjustment for SAWGAN-GP

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Hyperparameters were parameters set before training of the model, which had a

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significant impact on its learning and performance. This section optimized the

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performance of the SAWGAN-GP model in the generation task by adjusting

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hyperparameters. The adjustment could be waived for some of them as they did not

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need to be changed according to the model itself, or had been found in preliminary

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experiments to have relatively little impact on the stability and performance of the

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model. Table 6 showed these hyperparameters with fixed values.

367

Table 6. Hyperparameter with fixed values

Hyperparameter	Value
BATCH_SIZE (batch size)	32
IMAGE_SIZE (mage size)	128
CHANNELS_IMG (number of image channels)	3
Z_DIM (latent space dimension)	100
NUM_EPOCHS (training rounds)	300
FEATURES_DISC (number of discriminator features)	16
FEATURES_GEN (number of generator features)	16
LAMBDA_GP (gradient penalty coefficient)	12

368 The learning rate was a key hyperparameter, as a reasonable setting of the learning
369 rate could effectively improve the convergence speed of the model as well as the quality
370 of the generated image. A learning rate with an extremely high value could lead to
371 instability of model training, while an extremely low learning rate would increase the
372 training time. In the current experiment, focusing on the learning rate settings of the
373 generator and the discriminator, 10 different combinations of learning rates were
374 analyzed, as shown in Table 7.

375

Table 7. Combinations of different learning rates

Group number	LEARNING_RATE_G	LEARNING_RATE_D
A1	0.0001	0.0001
A2	0.0001	0.0004
A3	0.0001	0.0006
A4	0.0001	0.001
A5	0.00005	0.0002
A6	0.0002	0.0006

A7	0.0003	0.001
A8	0.00005	0.0004
A9	0.00005	0.0006
A10	0.0002	0.001

376 The learning rate of the generator was usually set lower than that of the
377 discriminator in these groups. This was because the structure of the generator had an
378 additional residual module, requiring a more refined learning pace. The loss curve after
379 the experiment was presented in Figure 8, and Table 8 showed the average loss and
380 training time of each group.

Figure 8. SAWGAN-GP loss at different learning rates

Table 8. Average loss and training time

Group number	Generator average loss	Discriminator average	Training time
		loss	
A1	31.603	0.527	8h 50m 07s
A2	54.406	0.709	9h 37m 57s
A3	41.194	0.679	8h 47m 18s
A4	42.981	0.627	9h 40m 33s
A5	45.487	0.923	9h 35m 46s

A6	42.667	0.571	8h 55m 19s
A7	32.837	0.506	9h 43m 46s
A8	54.758	0.845	9h 51m 49s
A9	48.622	0.884	9h 32m 27s
A10	17.891	0.451	9h 06m 24s

381 For the generator loss, the loss curves of most groups, except A2 and A5, tended
382 to converge as a whole and show a clear plateau period, with the loss value fluctuating
383 slightly during the iteration process. A3 entered the plateau period the earliest and
384 remained stable, indicating this group of generators was more efficient in learning
385 features. A7 and A9 entered the plateau period after nearly 4,000 iterations, suggesting
386 that the model may have encountered difficulties in the learning process, and the
387 possibility of further increases could not be ruled out. Groups A2 and A5 showed a clear
388 upward trend, indicating that the learning rate settings of these two groups failed to
389 effectively promote the generator to capture effective features, resulting in the failure
390 of stable convergence in the later stages of training, and even of producing
391 unsatisfactory results. Although the overall loss value of the A10 group was low,
392 indicating its good ability to learn concrete defect features, its loss curve fluctuated
393 seriously, which suggested an instability issue in the generation process.

394 The discriminator loss of all groups generally remained stable, and the loss value
395 showed a gradual downward trend during the training process, which tended to be stable.
396 This suggested that the model effectively learned the characteristic differences between
397 real samples and generated samples during the training process, and was able to
398 distinguish them well. Although all groups showed convergence, the results of the best

399 group, A10 (loss value 0.451), and the worst group, A5 (loss value 0.923) differed by
400 nearly twice, indicating the performance differences of the model under different
401 learning rate combinations.

402 Among all groups, the difference in training time was not significant. The shortest
403 training time was about 8 hours and 50 minutes (group A1), and the longest training
404 time was 9 hours and 51 minutes (group A8). The similarity of training time showed
405 that different settings of learning rate had minimal impact on the training process. But
406 it also suggested that more efficient training strategies could be explored in subsequent
407 studies to shorten the training time. Overall, group A3 exhibited the best performance.
408 After determining the optimal learning rate combination, each defect was generated
409 separately, and the corresponding loss value was recorded, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Losses of various defects in group A3

410 4.2. FID comparison

411 Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) **Error! Reference source not found.** was an
 412 image quality evaluation metric that had been widely used in recent years. FID not only
 413 focused on the diversity of generated images, but also evaluated their quality by
 414 calculating the distance between the generated images and the real images in the feature
 415 space. FID measured the quality of generated images by treating the feature vectors of
 416 the generated images and the real images as Gaussian distributions, and calculating the
 417 Fréchet distance between their means and covariances. The formula was as follows:

418
$$FID = \|\mu_r - \mu_g\|^2 + \text{Tr}(\Sigma_r + \Sigma_g - 2\Sigma_r\Sigma_g)^{1/2}$$

419 where μ_r is the mean of the real image; Σ_r is the covariance of the real image; μ_g is the
420 mean of the generated image; Σ_g is the covariance of the generated image. FID could
421 measure the similarity between the generated image and the real image regarding high-
422 level features. A considerable advantage of FID was that it not only evaluated the
423 diversity of generated images, but also captured the differences in image details. For
424 example, when the generated image lacks details, the FID value would increase,
425 indicating a problem with the image quality. Conversely, the smaller the FID value, the
426 higher the similarity. In addition, FID could also distinguish the phenomenon of
427 extremely high similarity of the generated images (i.e., mode collapse in the generated
428 images), which could cause insufficient generated diversity. Compared with IS, FID
429 was more accurate and performs better in many practical applications.

430 The comparison of FID in Figure 10 revealed the advantages and disadvantages of
431 different GAN architectures. With the advantage of Wasserstein loss, WGAN's FID
432 value dropped from 2,000 to approximately 800. Although there were some fluctuations,
433 its steady decline indicated the gradually improved quality of generated images, which
434 could avoid gradient vanishing and mode collapse, performing better than traditional
435 models. DCGAN used deep convolutional structures to improve generation capability.
436 Nevertheless, owing to the defects of JS divergence, its FID frequently oscillated
437 around 1,300, resulting in instability of generation. ACGAN improved label accuracy
438 through integrating generation and classification tasks, but its dual goals caused
439 gradient conflicts, resulting in FID values of more than 1,500 with the largest

440 fluctuations. This issue especially affects the distribution fitting of the generator at low
 441 iterations. In the improved WGAN architecture, SAWGAN's FID continued to decline
 442 and the fluctuations decreased, eventually reaching 307.08, which suggested that the
 443 quality of generated images had been effectively improved. WGAN-GP introduced a
 444 gradient penalty mechanism to stabilize FID in the later stages of training, with a
 445 minimum FID of 152.52, showing better stability. The most outstanding approach was
 446 SAWGAN-GP, whose FID continued to decrease during training which eventually
 447 reached 140.25, presenting excellent performance in generation quality and diversity.
 448 Without large fluctuations, the results demonstrated its excellent ability in feature
 449 capture and generation consistency.

450

Figure 10. Comparison of FID indicators

451

Table 9. Minimum FID values of different models

Model	FID
WGAN	682.07
SAWGAN	307.08
WGAN-GP	152.52

452 4.3. *Quality of image generation*453 4.3.1. *Basic model*

454 At Epoch 1, the images generated by ACGAN and DCGAN were quite blurry
455 without details. After 300 Epochs of training, the quality of images generated improved,
456 but it was still not comparable to WGAN. The images generated by WGAN at the same
457 training rounds showed obvious details and realism, and could capture the surface
458 characteristics of plain concrete.

(a) ACGAN generation quality

(b) DCGAN generation quality

(c) WGAN generation quality

Figure 11. Generation quality of basic models

459 *4.3.2. Improved model*

460 Compared to the generated images of WGAN (Figure 10c), the edges of defects,
 461 such as cracks and holes of SAWGAN (Figure 11a) and WGAN-GP (Figure 11b),
 462 gradually became more obvious in the same training stage, and the details were better
 463 presented, showing its advantages in capturing complex features. However, there were
 464 still some missing details and corrosion in the image. The generation quality of
 465 SAWGAN-GP (Figure 11c) was the most significant, reaching excellent quality after
 466 300 epochs, which presented extremely high clarity and rich details.

(a) SAWGAN generation quality

(b) WGAN-GP generation quality

(c) SAWGAN-GP generation quality

Figure 12. Generation quality of improved models

467 *4.4. Performance of SAWGAN-GP in classification model*

468 This section evaluated the authenticity of the data generated by SAWGAN-GP,
 469 and the ability of the classification model to identify the generated data. First, real
 470 defect images of fair-faced concrete were used to train the classification model.
 471 Thereafter, the images generated by SAWGAN-GP were input into the trained model
 472 as "unfamiliar data" to observe the model's recognition of the generated images.

473 The classification model was built using the pre-trained DarkNet-53 network,
 474 whose last fully connected layer and classification layer were replaced to adapt to the
 475 appearance classification task for fair-faced concrete. After 85 minutes of training, the

476 DarkNet-53 model achieved an accuracy of 98.11% on the validation set, demonstrating
477 the model's good performance on this task. Figure 13 showed the changes in accuracy
478 and loss curves during training.

479

480

Figure 13. Training process of DarkNet-53

481 After model training, this study further introduced images generated by
482 SAWGAN-GP for in-depth analysis to evaluate the authenticity of the generated images
483 and the classification ability of the model in different categories. Taking real images
484 and generated images as input, the trained DarkNet-53 model was used for the
485 evaluation of classification.

486 The comparison of evaluation indicators (Figure 14) illustrated that the DarkNet-
487 53 model generally maintained a high level of recognition ability for generated images.
488 Specifically, in most categories, the accuracy of generated images was similar to real
489 images. Table 10 showed more details that, in some categories, the accuracy of
490 generated images had been improved compared with the original images, especially in

491 holes and rust, where the accuracy of generated images was increased by 8.89% and
 492 2.04%, respectively. However, for some other categories, such as tieholes and seams
 493 (holines, velines), the accuracy of generated images has decreased by 12%, 10% and
 494 6%, respectively.

Figure 14. Comparison of test image evaluation indicators

495 Table 10. Comparison of accuracy between original image and generated image

Type	Original image accuracy	Generated image accuracy	Value-added
Alkaline	1	1	0
Crack	1	1	0
Hole	0.9	0.98	+8.89%
Holines	1	0.9	-10%
Rust	0.98	1	+2.04%
Spalling	0.98	1	+2.04%
Tiehole	1	0.88	-12%
Velines	1	0.94	-6%

496 In terms of recall and F1 score, the generated images showed obvious advantages
 497 in some categories, but also had some disadvantages in others. The largest increase in

498 recall occurred on the tiehole, which increased by 8% compared to the real image. The
 499 largest increase in F1 score was 5.26% for the horizontal seam lines (holines), while
 500 the largest decrease occurred on the crack, with a decrease in recall of 12.28% and a
 501 decrease in F1 score of 6.54%. In addition, the changes in other categories were
 502 relatively small. The generated images improved in some categories, including rust and
 503 spalling, with an increase of about 2% in both recall and F1 score.

504 Table 11. Comparison of recall rates between original images and generated images

Type	Recall rate of original images	Recall rate of generated images	Value-added
Alkaline	1	0.98039	+1.96%
Crack	1	0.87719	-12.28%
Hole	1	0.89091	-10.91%
Holines	1	1	0
Rust	0.98	1	+2.04%
Spalling	0.96078	0.98077	+2.08%
Tiehole	0.92593	1	+8%
Velines	1	1	0

505 Table 12. Comparison of F1 scores between original images and generated images

Type	F1 score of original image	F1 score of generated image	Value-added
Alkaline	1	0.9901	-0.99%
Crack	1	0.93458	-6.54%
Hole	0.94737	0.93333	-1.48%
Holines	1	0.94737	+5.26%
Rust	0.98	1	+2.04%

Spalling	0.9703	0.99029	+2.06%
Tiehole	0.96154	0.93617	-2.64%
Velines	1	0.96907	+3.09%

506 Figure 15 showed the confusion matrices of the generated images and real images
507 based on SAWGAN-GP. Although there was a small amount of confusion in some
508 categories of the generated images, the classification results of these two categories of
509 images were almost the same, showing good authenticity.

(a) Generated images

(b) Real images

Figure 15. Confusion matrix comparison of test images

510 Figure 16 further demonstrated the accuracy of DarkNet-53 in the classification of
511 generated images. By comparing the prediction results of generated images with real
512 images, the model was able to achieve high consistency in most categories, indicating
513 that the generated images were highly similar to real images in terms of vision and
514 feature distribution.

515

516

(a) DarkNet-53 prediction results for some real images

518

(b) DarkNet-53 prediction results for some generated images

519

Figure 16. Comparison of prediction results

520 5. Conclusions

521 To solve the problem of insufficient model generalization ability caused by the
522 scarcity of training data in the surface defect detection of fair-faced concrete, this paper
523 proposes a Wasserstein generative adversarial network (SAWGAN-GP) image
524 augmentation method based on self-attention mechanism and gradient penalty. Through
525 systematic experiments and multi-dimensional evaluation, the following conclusions
526 are drawn.

527 (1) SAWGAN-GP significantly improves the quality and diversity of image
528 generation:

529 The generation quality of SAWGAN-GP is significantly improved over the
530 comparison model through (a) introducing the self-attention mechanism to enhance
531 global feature perception, (b) combining the Wasserstein distance to optimize the
532 distribution difference metric, and (c) using the gradient penalty technology to stabilize
533 training. Experiments show that the FID value is reduced to 140.25, which is 79.4%,
534 54.3% and 8.0% lower than WGAN (682.07), SAWGAN (307.08) and WGAN-GP
535 (152.52), respectively. The generated images are outstanding in the restoration of
536 details of complex defects, such as cracks and holes, which can effectively solve the

537 blurring and distortion problems of traditional GANs.

538 (2) The gradient penalty mechanism significantly improves training stability:

539 The gradient penalty technology considerably suppresses training fluctuations by
540 constraining the Lipschitz continuity of the discriminator. The fluctuation range of
541 SAWGAN-GP's generator loss is reduced to 16.06, which is 39.4% lower than the
542 baseline model. The fluctuation range of the discriminator loss is only 1.45, which is
543 much lower than WGAN's 182.52. The hyperparameter optimization experiment
544 (Group A3) further verifies the robustness of the model to changes in the learning rate,
545 whose generator loss converges stably after 2,500 iterations.

546 (3) Generated data effectively improves defect classification accuracy:

547 Using the images generated by SAWGAN-GP for DarkNet-53 classification
548 model training, the recognition accuracy of key defect categories has been significantly
549 improved. The accuracy of hole defects has increased by 8.89% (from 90% to 98%),
550 and the accuracy of rust defects has increased by 2.04% (from 98% to 100%). Although
551 the accuracy of bolt holes and seams has decreased slightly (by 6% and 12%,
552 respectively), the overall F1 score still improved in some categories, such as horizontal
553 seams (by 5.26%) and rust (by 2.04%). The confusion matrix shows that the
554 classification results of generated images are highly consistent with those of real images,
555 demonstrating the effectiveness and visual authenticity of the generated data.

556 (4) A reliable solution for small sample defect detection is provided:

557 This method successfully solves the problem of model overfitting and insufficient
558 generalization ability owing to the scarcity of fair-faced concrete defect images.

559 Through generating high-quality and diverse defect samples (such as holes, rust, and
560 peeling), the original dataset is significantly expanded. The expansion can provide
561 scalable technical support for automated defect detection in industrial scenarios,
562 particularly for complex building structures where the collection of large-scale samples
563 can be difficult.

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565 Yidong Xu: Funding acquisition; Formal analysis; Investigation; Methodology;
566 Writing-original draft. Jiading Zhang: Formal analysis; Investigation; Writing-original
567 draft. Dongmin Lu: Formal analysis; Investigation; Resources; Methodology; Writing-
568 review & editing. Shi-Tong Li: Resources; Investigation; Writing-review & editing.
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571 **Declaration of Interest Statement**

572 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or
573 personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this
574 paper.

575 **Data availability**

576 Data will be made available on request.

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